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A STUDY ON WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN IT SECTOR

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Abstract:

Work life balance of women employees plays the major role because they have to manage their personal life for their good quality of life. The employee's satisfaction is based on the employee to be happy and deliver the level best. Even in the Worst scenario the employee is very loyal to their organization because of the employee Satisfaction. The quality of life is based on the professional life of each and every women employee who are coming forward to support to their family. The problem of the women employee's face is health condition, Pregnancy discrimination, Sexual harassment, no equal pay, etc. This paper says that how the women employees are balanced and Satisfied in IT sector and the factors that affect the work life balance of women employees are working hours, Job satisfaction, working condition, etc. and find out the women employee job satisfaction were analyzed by using statistical method that is Chi-square and Correlation test.

Keywords: Work Life Balance; Job Satisfaction; Personal Life and Professional Life.

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1. Introduction

In the current world the gender has no difference between them so both have the equal rights and knowledge. Women in the early century they won't even come out but after that mostly women participated in IT sector and show that equal strength and potential, they can do it by them self with out any help. So, some of the women where started their own business and running by there own and manage the company with effective knowledge. Here women employees who are all working in the different places and different work they do. But as an women entrepreneur there is no difficulty but want to face different type of problem to withstand in the market so the women employees are not like that because they no need to face problem but they want to keep the target per day and achieve that and face problem in their personal life and professional life. But it has become a tough challenge for women as they have to perform a lot of duties in home and even in the textile industries as well. As a working woman mostly, they have to get married at the particular time and that is the additional responsibilities and when they become mothers, they have to manage the primary care of the children. So, the extended family have the greater pressure to continue on

career coping up with competing demands of their multiple role. So, the process of making them pressure at work and after completing it that affects in their personal life. In the different sector mostly, the women health is affected because of standing for the whole day is not at all good for the human health. Health problems are likely lead to lower sales and performance of the working women. This paper focuses on the tough life of women employees were working in different sector.

2. Literature Review

J. Sudha (2014) research has identified the various aspects such as career advancement, Work stress, career aspiration, Work Family conflict and Family work conflict, child care in context with work life balance(WLB) and its practices and has revealed the overview of the various challenges and issues faced by Women employees to achieve WLB. K. Thrivenikumari & Dr. V. Rama Devi (2013) Work life balance as one of the most challenging issues being faced by the women employees in 21st century because of the type of roles they play at home and the spill over of personal life over professional life. The quality of life is being used by the organization as a strategic tool that has to attract and then retain the employees and give more importance to maintain their work life balance with equal level of performance and commitment at work(Shalini and bhawna 2012).(Sunitha Malhotra & sapna Sachdeva, 2005)in this paper they have said that the women are stepped into the work place but the roles and responsibilities are same and does not change, it still remains the same. More women are wearing multiple faces in their attempts to balance their both career and family responsibilities. (Nielsen survey, June 2011)In India women are mostly stressed and pressured for the time. Pleck's (1977)research have suggested that the family-to-work-spill-over is stronger only for the women and the work-to family-spill-over is stronger for the men.(Clark, 2000; Ungerson & Yeandle, 2005)work life balance teaches how to manage the dual career and solve with minimum conflict. The issue of work life balance has become the most hot topic in the current scenario. Work life balance can be difficult to achieve for full time women workers irrespective of work schedules especially for those with children (Williams, 2006).

Work life balance is the major thing in the employment as a dual career that is family and the work. The most important thing is to help the employees to achieve a balance between their work and also their home. Work life balance refers to the divergence between the work place demands and the demands of personal life. Prof. k. Santhana Lakshmi (March 2013) have examined that the educational institutions should address the Work life balance related issues among their staff, specifically women and take a holistic approach to design and implement the policies to support the teaching staff to manage their WLB. T.S. Shanthi & Dr. Sundar (January 2012) research measure about the level of satisfaction as perceived by the women-respondent employees on the varied determinants of Work life balance, to identify the major factors that influence the work life balance among various categories of women employees in I.T. Industry and to measure the overall work life balance of women employees irrespective of cadres. Satinder singh (2013) literature identifies its effect on various quality life condition i.e. Job Satisfaction, Work Stress, Career Growth, Turnover, Absenteeism, Appreciation and competitive environment in context with work life balance and its practices/ policies. In this paper, an endeavor has been made to provide an overview of various aspects of work life balance through the review of existing literature. Sobia shujat & Faryal (2011) studied and analyzed the impact of work life balance on employees job

satisfaction in private banking sector. Factor involved are job satisfaction and work life balance with respect to flexible working condition, work life balance program, employee intention to change/leave job, work pressure/stress and long working hours.

3. Objective

- 1) To identify the various factors like working hours, work involvement and family responsibility of women employees in their work life balance.
- 2) To study the effect of work life balance on quality of life of the women employee.
- 3) To study the work life balance of women employees across their demographic characteristic such as age group, number of children
- 4) To measure the work life balance on job satisfaction of women employees in IT sector.

4. Work Life Balance

The term work life balance was coined in 1986. Work life balance can be defined as achievement and enjoyment of all four life quadrants-Work, Family, Friends and self. Work life balance is to balance between the personal and professional life.

If the personal life is balanced then the professional life also balanced. Once the women employees are satisfied with their needs then they can manage their work life balance easily.

5. Factors Affecting Employee Satisfaction

Working Condition

They will be providing service for 7 days a week, 10 hours a day. The textile industries must provide the basic need of the women employees like drinking water, seating arrangements, healthy food facility only for the hostellers women employees who are coming from different places, clean and neat restroom and the working condition should be healthy and safety for the women employees.

Women Employee Benefits and Compensation

They provide the benefits if they achieve the target then they will provide the extra pay by the organization to increase the productivity. This motivates the employees to participate in all things to increase the performance of the individuals and also get the bonus, incentives etc

Work Load and Stress Level

Work load in IT sector is always high and there is a deadline for every project or document submission so that are impossible to reach some times so that occurs the job satisfaction to erode for even the most involved employees and it bring the higher job satisfaction to the work place.

There are many ways that arises the stress level of employees that are pressure from top management, other employee conflict, etc.. at the work place.

Conceptual Frame Work

6. Research Methodology

This research is based on the analytic in nature. The primary data were collected through the structured questionnaire. The study is based on the Work life balance and job satisfaction at different sector. The women employee satisfaction and retention of the respondents is recorded on 3 point Likert scale with Agree (3), Neutral (2), Disagree (1).

7. Description of the Tool Used

The questionnaire had 30 items. they are demographic variables are collected in detail no of respondents namely age group, number of children, Professional of spouse.

8. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data are analyzed by using the statistical tool. I have used Simple percentage Analysis and chi-square test and Correlation test. Which is used to find out the significant relationship between the dependent variables and independent variables and has its cross tabulation is mentioned below.

Marital Status	No of Responds	Percentage
single	25	41.66666667
married	35	58.33333333
total	60	100

This graph says that 58% are married women employees

Age	Respondents	Percentage
below 30	25	41.66667
30-40	22	36.66667
40-50	8	13.33333
above 50	5	8.33333
total	60	100

This graph says that the 41% are women employees age below 30

Flexible with working hours	Respondents	percentage
Agree	38	63.33333
Neutral	12	20
Disagree	10	16.66667
total	60	100

This graph says that 63% are satisfied with their working hours.

job satisfaction	Respondents	Percentage
agree	45	75
neutral	11	18.33333
disagree	4	4
total	60	100

This graph says that 75% of women employee are satisfied with their job

stress	Respondents	Percentage
Agree	22	36.66667
Neutral	14	23.33333
Disagree	24	40

This graph says that 36% of women employees are stressed

family problem	Respondents	Percentage
agree	14	14
neutral	26	43.33333
disagree	20	20

This graph says that 43% of women employees are neutral in the family problems

9. Chi-Square Analysis

1) Chi square test for job satisfaction and age

H0: There is no relationship between Job Satisfaction and Age

H1: There is relationship between Job Satisfaction and Age

Job Satisfaction * Age Crosstabulation						
Count						
		Age				Total
		Below 30	30-40	40-50	Above 50	
Job satisfaction	satisfied	25	6	0	0	31
	neutral	0	9	8	4	21
	dissatisfied	0	8	0	0	8
Total		25	23	8	4	60

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	56.634 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	67.363	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	19.051	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	60		

Thus the Result concluded that is H1 is Accepted. Hence there is relationship between the Job Satisfaction and Age.

2) Chi square for marital status and family problems

H0: There is no significant relation between marital status and family problems

H1: There is significant relation between marital status and family problems

Marital * Family Problem Crosstabulation					
Count					
		Family Problem			Total
		1.00	2.00	3.00	
marital	single	7	3	12	22
	married	7	11	20	38
Total		14	14	32	60

Chi-Square Tests		
	Value	df Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.481 ^a	2 .289
Likelihood Ratio	2.563	2 .278
Linear-by-Linear Association	.267	1 .605
N of Valid Cases	60	

Thus, the Result is concluded that is H0 is Accepted. Hence there is no relation between the marital and family problems.

10. Correlation Analysis

1) Correlation between Stress and Job Satisfaction

H0: $\rho=0$, There is no relationship between Stress and Job satisfaction

H1: $\rho \neq 0$, there is relationship between Stress and Job satisfaction

Correlations			
		Work Stress	Job Satisfaction
Work stress	Pearson Correlation	1	.645**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.645**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

Thus, the result is concluded that ρ is greater than 0. Hence there is positive relationship exist among the Stress and Job satisfaction.

2) Correlation between Age and working hours

H0: $\rho=0$, There is no relationship between Age and working hours

H1: $\rho \neq 0$, there is relationship between Age and working hours

Correlations			
		Age	Working Hours
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	.853**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Workinghours	Pearson Correlation	.853**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Thus, the result is concluded that ρ is greater than 0. Hence there is positive relationship exist among the Age and Working hours.

11. Findings of the Study

1) The Majority (58%) of the respondents are married women employees.

- 2) The Majority (41%) of the respondents are from the Age of Below 30.
- 3) The Majority (63%) of the respondents are agreed to their working hours are flexible.
- 4) The Majority (75%) of the respondents are agree that they are satisfied with their job.
- 5) The Majority (36%) of the respondents are agree that they are stressed.
- 6) The Majority (43%) of the respondents are neutral women employees have family problems.

Chi-Square Result

There is a Significant relationship between Age and Job Satisfaction.

There is a Significant relationship between Family problem and marital status.

Correlation Result

There is a positive relationship among Stress and Job Satisfaction

There is a positive relationship among Age and Working hours.

12. Conclusion

The work life balance of women employees plays a vital role in IT sectors. So, mostly in IT sector the women employee faces more difficulties in managing their personal life and professional life. The work life balance is influenced by different factors are demographic variables, individual variables. Thus, the women employee has to balance the both work and personal life, only the women employee should be satisfied with her job and get developed by themselves may lead to the good work life balance in current situation. In this paper it show that all women are balanced and they are satisfied with their jobs. Thus it is concluded that the – women employees in the IT sector have good WLB.

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